

with aluminum foil to prevent expansion of water caused by heating from the light source. After several water uptake readings, panicle area was measured with an automatic area meter. Transpiration was

estimated based on the area of exposed surfaces and on oven-dry weight. Results from both estimates (Fig. 2) showed that the cumulative water uptake or transpiration was linear.

This simple, inexpensive technique should be useful for studying the effects of environmental factors on water use by panicles and for investigations of genotypic variation in panicle water use. □

Rice-based cropping systems

Krishnamany — a new cowpea variety for the summer rice fallow

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Nearly 80,000 ha in Kerala have potential for increasing pulse production during summer rice fallow. The Government of Kerala is encouraging cowpea production. Harvesting cowpea is expensive because plants must be picked four or five times. A new cowpea variety, Krishnamany, has a very short flowering phase and requires only one or two pickings. It also withstands moisture stress, which is normal during the post-summer period.

Krishnamany is a black-seeded selec-

Performance of Kdnamany in summer rice fallow in Kerala, India

Variety	Seed yield (kg/ha)						
	Pattambi			Mannuthy	Karamana	Mean	per day
	1980	1981	1982	1982	1982		
Krishnamany	472	719	666	1118	602	715	13.75
Culture 17	465	693	664	1048	513	677	13.02
P. 118	133	323	503	840	250	410	6.95
Kolinji payar	435	478	479	1158	355	581	9.85
Pusa phalguni	402	581	444	790	243	492	8.34
EC 43721	310	576	567	830	306	518	8.78
CD (P = 0.05)	238	137	160	N. S.	160	—	—

tion from P. 118/Kolinjipayar. It has short duration (55-60 days), is bushy and nontrading, grows 30-35 cm tall, and produces 2-5 branches. Flowers are light violet and medium sized. Pods are about 11 cm long, dark green when immature,

and light brown when dry. There are about 10 seeds per pod, which weigh 70 g/1000. The variety is tolerant of yellow mosaic. Recommended seed rate is 20 kg/ha, with 20-30-10 kg NPK/ha. Performance data are in the table. □

Rice — wheat pattern for increased cereal production in alkali soils of eastern Uttar Pradesh

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Although much of eastern Uttar Pradesh is planted to cereals, production is low

because of alkaline soils. A rice — wheat cropping pattern was tested in alkali fields at the Kumarganj Crop Research Station from 1976 to 1978.

Soil was 54% sand, 22.3% silt, and 22.1% clay. CEC was 13.4 meq/100 g, ESP 81.6, pH 10.4, EC 2.1 mmho/cm in 1:2 soil:water suspension at 0-15 cm soil depth. Three replications of 5 × 4 m plots in a randomized block design were

established and soil was treated with 0, 3, 6, 9, and 12 t gypsum/ha or 0, 1.5, 3, 4.5, and 6 t pyrite/ha before the first transplanting. Less pyrite was applied because it contains 50% more sulfur than gypsum and is almost twice as expensive. Rice husk was applied with gypsum, and sawdust with pyrite at 0, 2.5, 5, and 7.5 t/ha. Dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) was grown and incorporated as green manure

Cereal grain production from rice — wheat crop sequence in alkali soils at Kumarganj, Faizabad, India

Application rate of soil amendments in 1976 (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)							
	1976-77		1977-78		1978-79		3-year average	
	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat
Gypsum								
0	1.0	1.0	1.6	1.1	2.0	1.1	1.5	1.1
3	2.0	2.4	2.9	2.1	3.4	2.1	2.8	2.2
6	3.5	3.4	4.6	3.0	4.7	2.9	4.3	3.1
9	4.8	4.3	6.0	3.7	6.2	3.6	5.7	3.9
12	5.3	4.8	6.4	4.2	6.8	4.2	6.2	4.4
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3

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Application rate of soil amendments in 1976 (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)							
	1976-77		1977-78		1978-79		3-year average	
	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat
Pyrite								
0	1.1	0.8	1.6	1.1	2.0	1.1	1.6	1.0
1.5	1.7	1.3	2.8	1.6	3.1	1.7	2.5	1.5
3.0	2.7	1.7	4.0	2.1	4.3	2.3	3.6	2.0
4.5	4.2	2.6	5.2	2.6	5.6	2.8	5.0	2.7
6.0	4.6	3.5	5.9	3.1	6.0	3.5	5.5	3.3
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4

in each of the 3 years.

IR24 (1976) and Jaya (1977 and 1978) seedlings were transplanted at 5 to 6 weeks at 15-cm spacing with 4 to 5 seedlings/hill. Nitrogen was applied at 120 kg/ha, with 22-26 kg P, 26-33 kg K, and 35-40 kg ZnSO₄/ha.

Wheat varieties HD1982 (1976) and HD1553 (1977 and 1978) were sown at

125 kg/ha in rows spaced 20 cm apart. Fertilization was 100 kg N, 17-28 kg P, 8-26 kg K, and 20 kg ZnSO₄/ha. To avoid termite damage, 16 kg BHC/ha was applied. Crops were irrigated when needed.

Rice husk and sawdust application did not affect rice or wheat yields. Yields in 1976 were 1 t rice/ha in untreated plots, 5.3 t in gypsum-treated plots, and

4.6 t in pyrite-treated plots. Wheat yields increased from 1 t/ha to 4.8 and 3.5 t/ha for gypsum- and pyrite-treated plots (see table).

Data showed a substantial residual effect of gypsum or pyrite treatment, and indicated a rice - wheat - green manure cropping pattern does not cause rapid reversion of reclaimed alkali soils.

Comparison of traditional and alternative cropping systems in Cagayan, Philippines

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Three maize-based cropping systems were compared for profitability with the farmer's pattern on the floodplains of Solana, Cagayan, Philippines. Profitability was measured by farm gross margin technique, which is the difference between gross farm income and current total variable costs (TVC) of production. The study was conducted during the 1981-82 dry and wet seasons. Each pattern was tested

in a 1,000-m² plot with 4 replications.

Mungbean yielded best during wet season because of a uniform rainfall pattern. The second mungbean crop suffered from declining rainfall after Dec. However, wet season crops often are flooded in early Aug when they are at critical growth stages.

Test crops planted in late Apr escaped flooding and heavy rainfall during critical growth stages, but not at harvesting stage.

In the traditional pattern yields of crops established later than mid-May are substantially reduced by heavy rain and flooding, especially on lower fields. Research showed that the physical environment of the area dictates early crop establishment and use of early maturing

varieties that resist damaged caused by flooding and drought.

Experimental maize - maize pattern yielded more than the farmer's maize - maize pattern in both seasons and had a higher return above TVC. Patterns with mungbean following or preceding maize, however, were most profitable, regardless of cultural manipulations. Return above TVC for patterns with mungbean ranged from \$582 to \$667.

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Cost-and-return analysis of traditional and alternative maize-based cropping systems in the river floodplains of Solana, Cagayan, Philippines, 1980-81 cropping season.

Cropping pattern		Yield (t/ha)		Gross return ^a (\$)	Total variable cost (\$)	Profit (GR - TVC) (\$)
First crop	Second crop	First crop	Second crop			
Maize	Maize ^b	2.0	0.8	408	163	245
Maize	Maize	2.1	1.4	591	194	397
Maize	Mungbean	2.6	1.0	928	346	582
Maize	Maize	1.2	2.4	1008	352	656

^a Based on current price right after harvest in the research barangay. ^b Farmer's pattern.